

Prevalence, Associated Factors and Outcomes of Spine Injuries Among Trauma Patients Admitted at the Muhimbili Orthopedic Institute (MOI) in 2024, Dar Es Salaam, Tanzania

Author: lana mohamed¹

Coordinator: alphonse simbila²

Affiliations:

¹ *university of medical sciences and technology*

² *muhimbili national hospital*

Introduction

With severe effects on people's physical, mental, and social well-being, spinal cord injury (SCI) continues to be a major cause of morbidity and disability globally. With an emphasis on patients undergoing emergency surgery, this study attempted to investigate the prevalence, contributing factors, and consequences of spinal cord injury in a hospital context.

Materials and Methods

This is a hospital-based cross-sectional chart review of all trauma patients admitted at MOI in 2024. The data is analyzed using (SPSS) version 23. Descriptive data is summarized as frequency, mean, and/or median, along with measures of spread. Chi-square test is used to determine associations between dependent and independent variables, and outcomes of spine injury among trauma patients.

Results

The study comprised 44 trauma patients with spinal injuries who were hospitalized to Muhimbili Orthopedic Institute (MOI) in 2024. Young adults between the ages of 20 and 39 made up the majority of patients (54.5%), with men making up the majority (77.3%). The most frequent spinal injuries were lumbar spine injuries (31.8%), followed by cervical spine injuries (29.5%) and multilayer spinal injuries (27.3%). The majority of patients (70.5%) had isolated spinal injuries without any accompanying trauma. Only one patient needed to be admitted to the intensive care unit, and inhospital mortality was modest (2.3%). Functional outcomes, however, were predominantly negative; none of the patients achieved a good outcome category, and 61.4% of patients were categorized as having bad outcomes.

Conclusion

Spinal injuries at the Muhimbili Orthopedic Institute in 2024 were mainly caused by lumbar and cervical spine trauma, predominantly affecting young, economically productive men. Although in-hospital survival was high, many patients experienced poor functional outcomes, creating a significant disability burden. Individual demographic or clinical factors did not strongly predict recovery, highlighting the importance of improving pre-hospital care, access to timely surgery and expansion of structured rehabilitation services in Tanzania

Keywords

cross-sectional, Muhimbili Orthopedics Institute, Spinal cord injury, Tanzania